

ARTS

HARMONIC ANALYSIS OF SCRIBIN'S PRELUDES OP.11: C MAJOR, A MINOR, E MINOR

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Kadıköy/İstanbul, Türkiye**Abstract**

The harmonic language of Alexander Scriabin's Preludes Op. 11 offers a vivid look into the composer's early stylistic approach, marked by extended tonal frameworks and inventive choices. This study focuses on three preludes – C Major, A Minor, and E Minor – exploring Scriabin's unique harmonic structures, sequencing techniques, and influences from Chopin. Each prelude embodies different facets of Scriabin's harmonic thought, from the use of pentachords and non-tertian structures in the C Major Prelude to sequential modulation and tonal shifts in the A Minor Prelude. The E Minor Prelude showcases Scriabin's innovative textural sequencing and vertical harmonies. Through these analyses, the study aims to demonstrate the complexities and nuances of Scriabin's early harmonic language, ultimately shedding light on his contributions to late Romantic music.

Keywords: Harmonic Analysis, Scriabin, Preludes Op. 11, Extended Tonal Frameworks, C Major, A Minor, E Minor, Pentachord, Non-tertian Structures, Sequential Modulation, Chromaticism, Late Romantic Music, Textural Sequencing, Vertical Harmonies, Chopin Influence, Cadential Zone, Tonal Shifts, Emotional Richness, Metrical Framework, Thematic Development.

In the early stages of Scriabin's career, harmony emerges as a defining feature of his stylistic approach. While adhering to the extended tonal framework of late Romanticism, the harmonic language in his compositions is filled with remarkable discoveries and audacious choices, often foreshadowing groundbreaking innovations to come.

Prelude No. 1 in C Major stands out as one of the most vivid depictions of "flight" in Scriabin's early oeuvre. The piece captures the composer's unique sense of inspiration while maintaining the tone of a personal, lyrical expression. In his mature and later works, the

concept of flight often serves as a transitional element between a contemplative mood and ecstatic triumph.

In Prelude No. 1 in C Major, harmony serves as a key element in the piece's figurative content, operating on multiple levels. The thematic core of the composition relies almost solely on the notes of the major pentatonic scale. Gentle dissonant harmonies arise between the voices, enriched by a wide register. Within the opening measures, a unique chordal phenomenon occurs – a non-tertian vertical structure is built over a pedal tone. This pentachord, however, should be viewed as an implied chord, serving as a suspension leading to a tonic triad.

Pic. 1. A. Scriabin - Prelude No. 1 in C Major, Op. 11, Measures 1-2

In a characteristic move, Scriabin employs a deliberate avoidance of strong metrical beats in the prelude, thereby shifting harmonic functions away from their traditional placement within the metrical framework. The deep bass and the first note of the melody in the

upper register land on an offbeat, while the metrical accent occurs on the third note, aligning with the first beat. As a result, the two accents neutralise each other. This technique, combined with other expressive means such as fluid tempo, transparent two-voice texture, ex-

pansive register, and the unique quintuplet figures, contributes to the ethereal lightness and a sense of weightlessness in the prelude. The form of the prelude in Op. 11 typically consists of a period with an extended second phrase, supplemented by a segment that reprises the initial phrase. The fragmentary structure that con-

cludes in the second phrase is shaped by intense harmonic development, progressing towards a dominant resolution. Notably, Scriabin employs disalteration in expanding the cadential zone, transitioning from an augmented DD43 chord to its standard form. This reveals the composition's luminous major tonality.

Pic. 2. A. Scriabin - Prelude No. 1 in C Major, Op. 11, Measures 13-18

Prelude No. 2 in A Minor showcases a range of features indicative of Scriabin's early harmonic thought. The sequence-based development of themes and sequences plays a significant role in shaping the composition's structure. The form is a straightforward two-part reprise with double periods. The initial four-measure thematic core is transposed to the natural dominant key of E Minor. In the reprise, it first appears in

A Minor, then shifts to D Minor, the key of the subdominant. This aligns with the classical tonic-subdominant-dominant-tonic (t-s-D-t) tonal structure; the quarto-fifth system is also typical for Scriabin. Notably, he employs a colourful sequential modulation in the second phrase of the first part, transitioning from A Minor to G-sharp Minor through enharmonic modulation.

Pic. 3. A. Scriabin - Prelude No. 2 in A Minor, Op. 11, Measures 20-21

The developmental section, constituting the first phrase of the second part, is also built on sequential development and is divided into two segments. The tonal scheme of this episode follows: E Minor - G Major - G Minor - B-flat Major. During the modulation from minor to its parallel major, the minor tonic serves as the

VI degree in the forthcoming key. The transition from G Major to G Minor is achieved by juxtaposition. The B-flat Major reached at the end of this section assumes the role of the Neapolitan subdominant of the primary key, naturally leading to the dominant thereafter.

Pic. 4. A. Scriabin - Prelude No. 2 in A Minor, Op. 11, Measures 57-65

The range of harmonic colours is crucial in shaping the Prelude's intricate, sensuous atmosphere. Notable are the numerous non-chord tones and suspensions that are characteristic of Scriabin, adding a particular edge. Alterations like the diminished fifth in DD7, D65, and D7, as well as the diminished third in VII65, significantly heighten tension. A purposeful distancing from the tonic is evident – it appears just twice, first in the fourth measure as a t6 and then at the composition's conclusion. Elliptical movements and secondary dominants are strung together in extended sequences, imbuing the piece with emotional richness and dynamic energy. Scriabin's early style is deeply rooted in the works of Chopin. A comparison between the A Minor Prelude

and Chopin's Mazurka in Op. 17, also in A Minor, reveals similarities not just in pianistic texture and melody, but also in harmonic devices. This includes the chromaticism in the voices and a deliberate avoidance of a stable tonic foundation.

Chopin's dominant sixth chord, reinterpreted by Scriabin, becomes the leitmotif of Prelude No. 4 in E Minor. Chronologically, this is the first piece in Op. 11, penned by the composer at the age of seventeen. The prelude is derived from a segment of an unfinished ballad in B Minor, for which Scriabin wrote the words, "Beautiful country! Life here is different!" While thematically resonant with the A Minor Prelude, this composition unveils a more intimate tone in its expression.

Pic. 5. A. Scriabin - Prelude No. 4 in E Minor, Op. 11, Measures 1-3

The originality of Scriabin's lyrical texture unfolds vividly. Textural layers are sequentially introduced – within a few beats, the texture thickens to four voices. Silence thus serves as an inception point for development. In this setting, harmony gains special expressiveness. The first significant vertical chord is a harmonic dominant with a sixth in the bass, appearing at a point when the modal sense is still undefined. This emphasises the chord's phonetic quality, imbuing it with a

mysterious, mystical hue through the augmented triad. This dominant sixth chord, in various incarnations, serves as the central harmonic element of the prelude, lending the piece a poignant, melancholic tone. In the cadenza, Scriabin breaks classical voicing rules, allowing the D7 seventh to rise while maintaining the bass on the dominant, thereby sidestepping a metrical and, ultimately, semantic resolution on the tonic.

Pic. 6: A. Scriabin - Prelude No. 4 in E Minor, Op. 11, Measures 4-9

Much like the Prelude in A Minor, sequencing is the central principle for material development in this miniature piece. The theme initially appears in E Minor and is subsequently transposed to B Minor, the key of the natural dominant. In the second half of the phrase, dynamism is fueled by an ascending chromatic sequence, where the voice count occasionally rises to five. In such instances, the bass note precedes the entire chord, sustaining a tie from the previous weak beat. This technique subtly veils both textural and metric weightiness.

In the second phrase, the cadence undergoes significant expansion. Following two parts of the sequence, an expressive pause occurs for the first time in the prelude. The VII7 chord, resolving to A Minor – the key of the subdominant – transforms into a Neapolitan subdominant sixth chord. The D7 in the cadenza is typically voiced without the fifth; moreover, the dominant reappears twice with the sixth in the bass, mirroring the prelude's beginning. The composition's introspective and contemplative mood is underscored by the melodic prominence of the fifth in the closing section.

Conclusion

In sum, the Preludes in C Major, A Minor, and E Minor from Scriabin's Op. 11 offer a compelling look into the composer's evolving harmonic sensibilities. These works intricately combine Romantic tonality with daring harmonic choices, serving as windows into both the historical musical landscape and the individual genius of Scriabin. The composer's penchant for complex harmonic structures—often nuanced, subtle, and layered—functions as both emotive device and structural element. From the ethereal qualities of the C Major Prelude to the poignant tensions in E Minor, Scriabin uses harmony as an expansive canvas to paint a range of human emotions and experiences. These compositions are not mere exercises in harmony; they are evocative, emotionally resonant works that manifest the limitless potentials of musical language. They bear witness to Scriabin's transformative approach to harmonic analysis, an approach that challenges, enriches, and ultimately extends the boundaries of musical understanding.

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